

Co-Creating Transformative Pathways to Biological and Ecosystem Ocean Observations
(BioEcoOcean)

Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

V2.0

Document Revision History

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Executive Summary

The DEC Plan is a living document updated periodically in response to research developments and evolving stakeholders' needs or their feedback. As such, it is an integral part of the project, designed to ensure that the project's results are widely disseminated, effectively exploited and clearly communicated. The Plan describes how the BioEcoOcean consortium engages with a diverse range of stakeholders, identified at the beginning of the project through a stakeholder mapping activity, utilizing a variety of dissemination, exploitation, and communication methods, to maximize the project impact, thus contributing to the advancement of knowledge, innovation, and policy in the field of biological and ecosystem ocean observations in the EU and globally.

The document describes the plan of dissemination activities, ranging from publications, conferences and workshops to use of online platforms, newsletters, webinars and policy briefs. The exploitation strategy focuses on the identification of key exploitable results (KERs), exploitable pathways, stakeholder engagements, and intellectual property management. The communication plan outlines clear and consistent messaging emphasizing the BioEcoOcean objectives, results and their impact, with details on different communication channels to be employed in the project. Finally, the DEC Plan describes the process of regular monitoring and evaluation of DEC activities to assess their effectiveness and impact. Key performance indicators (KPIs) will be established, including metrics such as the number of publications, attendance at events, website traffic, social media engagement, and uptake of project results.

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AIR Centre	Atlantic International Research Centre
BGC	Biogeochemistry
BioEco	Biological and Ecological
BIOS	Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science
CA	Consortium Agreement
CORDIS	The Community Research and Development Information Service
CoPF	Community of Practice Forum
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DoA	Description of Action
EBV	Essential Biodiversity Variable
ECOTIP	European Ocean Observing System

ECV	Essential Climate Variable
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EO	Expected Outcome
EOV	Essential Ocean Variable
EV	Essential Variable
ESM	Earth System Model
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
IUCN	The International Union for Conservation of Nature
IOPAN	Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KIP	Key Impact Pathway
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MBON	Marine Biodiversity Observation Network
MPA	Marine Protected Area
NGO	Non-governmental organization
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
ObsSea4Clim	Ocean observations and indicators for climate and assessments
OSPAR	Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic
OTGA	Ocean Teacher Global Academy
R&D	Research and Development
SC	Steering Committee
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
UN	United Nations
UNEP	The United Nations Environment Programme
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UU	Uppsala University
WI	Wider Impact
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The BioEcoOcean DEC Plan describes strategies and actions which will be implemented to maximize the project's impact while ensuring alignment with EU requirements. The main objectives of the BioEcoOcean DEC Plan are:

Dissemination: To share the project results which contribute to advancing sustained Biology and Ecosystems (BioEco) observations of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) with the scientific community, industry, policymakers, and other relevant stakeholders to advance knowledge and stimulate further research and innovation.

Exploitation: To ensure practical utilization of project Key Exploitable Results (KERs), in particular the Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science (BIOS), by the BioEcoOcean target stakeholder groups during and in the years after the project completion,

Communication: To raise awareness about the project activities, outputs and their impact among the scientific and non-scientific audiences, through a set of efficient and engaging communication activities and resources.

The DEC activities and strategies are driven by the need to maximize the impact of the BioEcoOcean project according to its overall objectives which are to:

- ◆ Co-create a comprehensive, fit-for-purpose, and inclusive BIOS that promotes a holistic approach, fosters effective communication and collaboration among stakeholders and sectors, and enables interoperability.
Deliverables: 2.2, 2.4, 2.5, 2.6, 4.4, 5.1 and 5.2
- ◆ Accelerate and improve the implementation and usage of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) for biology and ecosystems, while ensuring seamless interoperability with Essential Climate and Biodiversity Variables (ECVs and EBVs), to drive progress towards global biodiversity, ecosystem and climate assessments.
Deliverables: 2.1, 2.3, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2 and 4.5
- ◆ Strengthen the development of common approaches, standards and inter-calibrated protocols for the BioEco EOV and ECV observations, modelling and reporting.
Deliverables: 3.2, 3.5, 4.1
- ◆ Improve understanding of the links between ocean biodiversity, biogeochemistry and climate by incorporating co-creation, interdisciplinary approaches, and cutting-edge technology and modelling.
Deliverables: 3.3, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.3
- ◆ Harness observation networks to improve scientific understanding of the causes of biodiversity loss, including the compound effects of multiple anthropogenic stressors, climate change and disturbance regimes driving ecosystems beyond tipping points.

Deliverables: 4.2, 4.4

- ◆ Enhance evidence-based decision-making that can inform future planning and support adaptive management of future conditions to sustain ecosystems and human well-being by co-creating and demonstrating operational and interconnected workflows, from observing system review and design to policy application.

Deliverables: 2.5, 2.6, 4.4, 4.5, 4.6

- ◆ Enhance operational global observing and forecasting systems by prioritising capacity building for diverse stakeholders, including training courses, workshops and dissemination activities.

Deliverables: 5.1, 5.2, 6.3, 6.4, 6.6

The DEC Plan is a living document updated as often as needed in response to project research developments and updates to stakeholder engagement needs. This initial version builds upon and is faithful to the BioEcoOcean Grant Agreement (GA) Description of Action (DoA), augmented by significant developments in the project communication plan and resources, initial stakeholder mapping (MS6.1) and improved linkages to Data Management Plan (DMP; D1.1).

The DEC Plan is also intended as a pragmatic guide to the BioEcoOcean consortium partners on how to maximize the potential of the DEC tools and resources made available by the Commission as well as the project itself.

An online version of the DEC Plan will always be available on the project intranet to allow for posting comments and edits from each project member in a collaborative mode. All suggestions will be periodically reviewed by WP6, and versions with accepted major revisions will be published at least every 18 months on the BioEcoOcean community page of the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/communities/bioecoocean/>), with an individually assigned DOI to each version on top of a single DOI that always leads to the most recent version.

BioEcoOcean's WP6 is responsible for overseeing the DEC Strategy and its implementation plan, with all partner institutions contributing with various and complementary roles. Table 1 identifies project members acting as focal points for different DEC elements.

Table 1: Focal points for DEC activities in BioEcoOcean.

Role	Name, Partner
WP6 Leader	Temporarily: Artur Palacz and Dominik Krzyminski, IO PAN
Communications Officer, Dissemination Consultant	Artur Palacz, IO PAN
Communications Officer, Social Media and Website Manager	Dominik Krzymiński, IO PAN
Stakeholder Engagement Consultant	Joana Soares, AIR Centre

Data Manager and Data Protection Officer	Elizabeth Lawrence, UNESCO
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2. Anticipated project impact

BioEcoOcean will provide a test bed for co-creative operational BioEco ocean observing with potential for global uptake. To ensure the significance of its contribution to the expected outcomes (EO) and wider impacts (WI) set out in the Call Topic *HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-8 - Closing the research gaps on Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) in support of global assessments*, the project will, among other things, develop and promote the uptake of the comprehensive BIOS. BIOS will boost the ability to establish operational workflows for biology and ecosystem EVs, and guide the development of a more holistic, transparent, and fit-for-purpose ocean observing system. The Blueprint will be honed through the BioEcoOcean Living Labs (WP3-4) and through the active involvement of the international scientific community, and key target stakeholders such as the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) Biology & Ecosystems and Biogeochemistry Panels of Experts, the Marine Biodiversity Observing Network (MBON), and the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS). This will ensure that the Blueprint and the advances to the EOVs (e.g. through the revised BioEco EOVS Specification Sheets) will have international exposure and will support change in the global BioEco observing community. The long-term legacy of the project's outcomes will be through increased coordination and collaboration among target stakeholders, leading to more effective and efficient ocean observations from local to global scales.

Figure 1: The results of BioEcoOcean, and how they lead to EO and WI. The main pathways leading from results to outcomes, and outcomes to wider impacts are indicated along blue arrows.

Figure 1 summarizes the BioEcoOcean’s unique contributions and pathways to the delivery of EO and WI, with the EO/ research results including but not being limited to:

- ◆ Improved ability of EOVs (with a special focus on 6 EOVs) to detect loss of resilience due to climate change and multiple stressors, thus supporting policy for rapid decisions and mitigation actions;
- ◆ Harmonization of innovative sampling across focal living labs (6 labs);
- ◆ Optimized sampling design and power curves to reliably detect multiple scenarios of change;
- ◆ New understanding and capacity to generate scenario-based model projections (including climate change scenarios) of the role of changing biology (6 EOVs) in regulating carbon sequestration, performed on global scale with significant potential to improve future ESM projections and the global assessments relying on them;
- ◆ Addition of socio-economic variables along with environmental variables to understand drivers of ecosystem change and provide a more complete understanding of cumulative impacts that can inform future management.

All in all, BioEcoOcean will increase the Technological Readiness Level (TRL) of BioEco EOVs from concept level (TRL 1-3) and pilot level (TRL 4-6) to pilot and/or mature level (TRL 5-7), making the system more efficient and operational to better deliver required information for policy and decision makers.

Tables 2 and 3 summarize the project’s contribution to expected outcomes and wider impacts anticipated by the project. A more detailed description of these linkages can be found in BioEcoOcean’s GA DoA document.

Table 2: Anticipated contribution to the Expected Outcomes through key project results, including KERs which are listed in Section 6.

Expected Outcomes (EO)	Key project results
<u>EO1: EO/ Development</u> Further developed key ocean monitoring indicators, ECVs, EOVs that support global assessments and foster the development of ocean climate monitoring and reporting	Adoption of the Blueprint for a fit-for-purpose ocean observing system → KER#1
	Advancement in the development of all GOOS BioEco EOVs with focus on gaps in Plankton and Marine Habitat ECVs and associated EBVs → KER#2
	Co-creation in living labs and stakeholder interaction to support the development of biological ocean and climate indicators derived from EVs → KER#4
<u>EO2: Improved ESMs</u>	Strengthening of forecasting tools for pelagic ecosystems and carbon fluxes → KER#3

Further improved ESMs representing key physical, biogeochemical and biological processes in the ocean with reduced uncertainty of climate change projections at regional scales, and reduced biases	High sensitivity analysis on zooplankton and micronekton functional diversity effects → KER#3
	Identification of key priorities for advancing biological and ecological realism in models and providing recommendations on EOVs data needs and model designs → KER#3, KER#6
<u>EO3: Understanding biodiversity links and stressors</u> Linkages between ocean physical, biogeochemical and biodiversity, variability over time, and the impacts and interaction of stressors on ocean health, adaptation and resilience of ecosystems	Blueprint co-creation integrating biological, physical, and BGC expertise → KER#1
	Estimates of biological responses to environmental stressors through living labs → KER#3, KER#4
	Requirements for co-located sampling of multiple EOVs and associated co-designed sampling schemes → KER#2, KER#6
	Ensuring knowledge transfer and capacity development for maintaining interdisciplinary linkage → KER#1
<u>EO4: Climate standards & climate change mitigation</u> Strengthened development of common, agreed standards for climate records content, format, quality and validation methodology	New datasets for Plankton and Marine Habitat Properties ECVs and corresponding EOVs → KER#5, KER#6
	Recommendations for priority biological data products to advance ocean carbon and climate modelling → KER#6
	Development of a protocol for scientific validation of biological and ecosystem models in collaboration with international bodies → KER#3
<u>EO5: Evidence-based decision making & sustainable resource management</u> Enabled evidence-based decision-making; European leadership in ocean-climate-biodiversity science nexus; Significant contribution to the implementation of European and global agendas	Strengthening the BioEco ocean observing system to deliver information, promote sustainability, and support policy decisions → KER#1, KER#2
	Support for the implementation of EU directives, particularly the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive → KER#1, KER#4
	Delivery of high-quality standardised data for advanced scientific knowledge and science-based decision-making → KER#4, KER#5, KER#6
	Strengthened European leadership through the co-creation process with stakeholders and established global actors in EOVS development → KER#1

Table 3: Anticipated contribution to the Wider Impacts through key project results with identified key impact pathways. Relevant project deliverables are also listed explicitly in this table.

Wider Impacts (WI)	Key project results (deliverables)	Key Impact Pathways
WI-1: Better understanding and strengthening of the mitigation potential of ecosystems and sectors based on the sustainable management of natural resources	Next-generation ecosystem models (D3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.5)	Data-informed management practices enhanced by new models and tools.
	Training of stakeholders (D2.4, 5.1, 5.2)	Training ensures better streamlined BioEco observing system data for sustainable management at various levels.
	New observation tools and spatial indicators (D3.1, 3.4, 4.6)	
WI-2: Support the adaptation and resilience of ecosystems, as well as economic sectors in the context of the changing climate	Updated EOVS specification sheets (D2.3, 3.1, 3.2)	Optimized BioEco observing system using emerging tools and methods to enhance understanding and support resilience.
	New technologies for real-time biodiversity assessment (D3.2, 3.4)	Engaging stakeholders ensures comprehensive approach in addressing biodiversity change drivers.
	Improved observations for Marine Spatial Planning (D3.2, 3.4, 3.8, 4.2)	
	Stakeholder engagement activities (D4.4, 5.1, 5.2, 6.4, 6.5, 6.6)	
	Environmental, social, and economic variable identification (D3.8)	
WI-3: Efficient support systems and projections to derive solutions for tackling threats and support decision-making and adaptation policies	Increased access to harmonised, interoperable data (D1.5, 4.4, 4.5)	Decision-support system integrating data and models for science-based decision-making.
	Blueprint for operational workflows (D2.5)	Blueprint involves stakeholders to bridge data providers and users, improving information support systems.
	Scenario-based projections (D3.5, 4.6)	
	Monitoring socio-economic and environmental variables (D3.8)	
WI-4: Increased climate change mitigation in the primary sectors	Knowledge and tools for understanding carbon uptake and storage (D3.3, 3.7, 4.3)	Ecosystem models and Marine Organic Carbon Atlas to evaluate mitigation scenarios.
	Importance of socio-economic and environmental monitoring (D3.8)	Blueprint facilitates socio-economic and environmental considerations in designing climate change policies.

WI-5: Improved capacity to climate change of natural systems and related sectors	Knowledge and tools for understanding carbon uptake and storage (D3.3, 3.5, 3.7, 4.3)	Models to test carbon sequestration scenarios and identify restoration sites. Marine Organic Carbon Atlas links biodiversity with carbon cycling, enhancing nature-based solutions against climate change.
WI-6: Sustainable management of scarce resources, mitigating climate related risks	Updated EOV specification sheets (D2.3)	Blueprint framework ensures best practices in data collection and analysis, connecting science and research to marine management. Results provide guidance for EU directives and enhance evidence-based decision-making.
	Experimental designs for detecting changes (D4.2)	
	Operational workflows for forecasting tools (D3.3, 3.4, 3.6, 3.8, 4.6)	
	Inclusion of socio-economic variables in EOV framework (D3.8)	

3. Target audiences and stakeholder engagement

The BioEcoOcean DEC Plan takes into account the importance of stakeholder involvement and inputs for effective marine biodiversity monitoring and comprehending user and policy needs. The insights and perspectives of diverse groups contribute significantly to a holistic understanding of marine biodiversity issues which are central to the project objectives.

BioEcoOcean emphasizes co-creation with diverse stakeholders to develop BIOS and other research outcomes while ensuring approaches are appropriate and aligned with both environmental and stakeholder needs. The project was set up to identify and engage with stakeholders involved in ocean and biodiversity observation and management, from local to national to global levels. BioEcoOcean has identified and mapped coastal and marine stakeholder groups that actively engage within their local community advancing data collection, monitoring, dataflows, and models for BioEco EOVs. Furthermore, BioEcoOcean seeks to collaborate with global ocean observation initiatives as with the overall biodiversity monitoring community, which seeks to develop a global framework for biodiversity monitoring, to ensure wide discussion and adoption of its co-produced standards. The overall goal is to enhance the co-creation, sharing, and adoption of BioEcoOcean-related knowledge outputs, thereby extending its benefits to a wider range of stakeholders.

3.1. Definition of the target audience

Following the quintuple helix model, the audiences identified below represent the relevant actors whom BioEcoOcean will target, strengthening connections between research, business, government, citizens

(society) and environment, as well as media, to advance knowledge, monitoring and conservation of marine ecosystems (table 4).

Table 4. BioEcoOcean target audience list and associated engagement goals.

Audience	Includes	Engagement goal
International organizations	Multilateral organizations (e.g., UNEP, IOC, IUCN), international partnerships and agreements (e.g., OSPAR)	Create international linkages beyond the EU to exchange information, best practices, technologies, and solutions at a global level
Governmental bodies	Policy and decision-makers operating at different scales (EU, national, regional and local levels), MPA management authorities	Disseminate BioEcoOcean results outputs and activities, ensuring global coverage and increased awareness, and support policy-making decisions
Academia	Projects, programs, networks, research organizations	Increase awareness of BioEcoOcean activities amongst the R&D community and promote networking
Industry and private sector	Business, across industries (e.g., fisheries, oil and gas, tourism, etc.)	Broaden dissemination and exploitation opportunities and assess the potential of the solutions from BioEcoOcean in a market context
Civil society	Local community groups, NGOs, associations	Promote horizontal knowledge dissemination and engage society as a whole
Media	Online news outlets, social media	Disseminate BioEcoOcean results, targeting national and international media

3.2 Initial stakeholder mapping exercise

Stakeholder analysis is a powerful process for identifying stakeholder groups, working to understand their

interest in and influence on the project, and prioritizing them to support stakeholders' engagement and management activities.

A stakeholder analysis was performed with the BioEcoOcean consortium during the project's first in-person meeting at IOPAN, in Sopot, Poland, in the first week of May 2024. The exercise was conducted using the interactive online tool Miro which also facilitated the involvement of consortium members who only attended the event online.

The exercise followed a classic stakeholder mapping and analysis process using conceptual methodologies and tools such as Cluster Diagram, Power-Interest Grid, and MoSCoW prioritization. A multi-step approach was used to:

- ◆ list stakeholders – build clusters,
- ◆ identify interest and influence,
- ◆ create stakeholders' categories, and
- ◆ start creating a list of engagement activities.

The outcomes of the exercise served as input for the creation of the BioEcoOcean stakeholders database and were made available to the project consortium via the project's intranet in SharePoint.

3.3 Initial BioEcoOcean stakeholders database

After the initial stakeholder mapping exercise an online spreadsheet was created with the identified stakeholder groups as well as an initial list of proposed stakeholder engagement activities. Stakeholder mapping is a continuous process; therefore, the initial stakeholder database has been expanded and updated in conjunction with the project partners, to capture additional stakeholders' as well as relevant information in support of stakeholder engagement efforts.

The initial stakeholder database is also available in detail at the project SharePoint, allowing for easy feedback and evolution over the duration of the project. The consortium partners support this activity and cross-reference it to ensure potential new stakeholders, and stakeholder information drilled down according to region, sector and current level of importance/interest, are captured in the stakeholder mapping update. A finalized revised version will be delivered in M28-30.

The BioEcoOcean team has been engaging with the identified stakeholders primarily establishing contact with the groups and building trust to reinforce the move towards them (stakeholder support), while leveraging on a series of activities (e.g. webinars – the Marine Biodiversity Networking Fridays, workshops and others) focusing on developing cooperation between the stakeholder community to:

- ◆ Exchange and transfer experience and knowledge outputs;

- ◆ Share knowledge and best practices;
- ◆ Promote capacity building;
- ◆ Set the basis for setting up the Blueprint network, and
- ◆ Reflect on its longevity and sustainability after the project lifetime; while raising awareness to the project and supporting the stakeholder needs.

The Stakeholder Mapping, Engagement and Outreach task planned to leverage the Marine Biodiversity Networking Fridays webinars to engage with different stakeholder groups. The first webinar was organized on the 11th of April 2025 focusing on the co-creative process of developing the BioEcoOcean Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science. Additionally, a series of webinars focusing on the different Biology and Ecosystems Essential Ocean Variables (GOOS BioEco EOVs) is running from July to December 2025 and will provide an introduction to the BioEco EOVs, their importance for monitoring biodiversity and decision making. The first introductory webinar hosted by the Marine Biodiversity Networking Fridays occurred on July 11th, 2025.

4. Communication

The communication plan is driven by the completed initial mapping of stakeholders and the analysis of their informational needs (Section 3). The communication plan includes a description of the internal communication measures implemented to date and outlines the plan for external communication by detailing key messages and corresponding communication activities and channels to reach the target audiences.

4.1 Internal communication

BioEcoOcean ensures smooth implementation of the project objectives by establishing and maintaining state-of-the-art measures to ensure efficient and frequent internal communication. Project partners are equipped with clear guidelines and access to a common cloud-based content management system and collaboration platform to maximize indirect communication. Additionally, virtual and in-person meetings will be arranged at different frequencies and sizes, to ensure sufficient direct communication between project partners. The following measures have already been put in place as part of the BioEcoOcean internal communication plan.

Online collaboration platforms

In the project's initial weeks, UU established a dedicated SharePoint facility for all project partners to serve as project intranet and a primary online platform for communication and collaboration. SharePoint also provides a common online files and information storage system, including for data exchange. Each partner ensures that there is good housekeeping when it comes to storing, organizing, and sharing information, applications, and any

relevant services across the project consortium. The project intranet adheres to current requirements for online safety protocols, requiring two-step authentication for access.

UU set up the top-level file structure. Each WP uses dedicated folders to organize work and keep records of project developments at all stages. This helps, for instance, incoming project members quickly understand the status and progress of tasks. Partners are encouraged to use SharePoint as much as possible instead of email discussions threads and email file exchanges which are difficult to track and access.

Each partner is obliged to inform the project coordination office about any new project members affiliated with their institution, so that UU can set up access for all new users as soon as possible.

In addition, the consortium has access to an email list with contact information to all project partners which can be viewed and downloaded from SharePoint. This list is kept up to date by all the partners as per project's Consortium Agreement (CA). UU will take care of the everyday internal communication. However, any project member can contact the entire consortium as needed.

Project members are also encouraged to use any virtual meeting platform they prefer if it can be accessed by all meeting invitees (e.g. Zoom, MS Teams). General rule: the person or institution organizing the meeting is responsible for choosing the platform.

Meetings

Three types of official and regular internal meetings are arranged:

- ◆ **Steering Committee (SC) meetings:** Held monthly online, with minutes posted on SharePoint. These meetings help identify and resolve any issues with the work plan promptly.
- ◆ **General Assembly meetings:** Two per year, one in person and one online, approximately ca. 6 months apart. These meetings discuss and decide on important matters. General rules on General Assembly participation are described in the CA.
- ◆ **Work Package meetings:** Held as needed and called by WP leads and members. Initially conducted monthly, these meetings are expected to be reduced to bi-monthly after the project's first year.

4.2 External communication

4.2.1. Key messages

BioEcoOcean's external communication plan emphasizes the project's impact on ocean monitoring, data accessibility, collaborative efforts, and biodiversity and climate resilience, aligned with project objectives. The plan includes four key messages to guide our external communication efforts.

Message #1:

"We unite diverse stakeholders to co-create a shared plan to enhance the value and impact of ocean observations."

How do we collaborate for a better understanding of life in the ocean? How do we enable and facilitate communication at different scales and across sectors?

BioEcoOcean co-creates an inclusive Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science to enhance stakeholder collaboration and data interoperability. The Blueprint Living Lab is a collaborative platform for developing a guiding tool: the Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science, focusing on marine life. This innovative product will be co-created with the global ocean observing community, with contributions via for example surveys, workshops and testing the Blueprint. The aim is to foster a more holistic and collaborative approach to ocean observations. Development will take place through a co-creative process inviting the global community, especially those interested in biology and ecosystem ocean observation. Progress on the development of the Blueprint and associated resources can be viewed on the project website here: <https://bioecocean.org/actions/blueprint-living-lab/>; and tracked live on the social media channels.

Message #2:

"The effective use of essential ocean data is crucial for better understanding and protecting marine life and climate. "

BioEcoOcean accelerates the use of Essential Ocean Variables, aiming to integrate them with climate and biodiversity variables for comprehensive global assessments. BioEcoOcean research on EOVs is carried out through six focal living labs, each focusing on advancing observations of specific BioEco EOVs through addressing research questions relevant for a specific environmental setting while taking into consideration the entire ocean value chain, from observing system design to policy application. Up to date information on EOv research progress in the project can be viewed from the project website at: <https://bioecocean.org/actions/focal-living-labs/>

All data and information collected will be freely and openly available through regional and global portals, such as OBIS, EMODnet, and GitHub, ensuring their validation and reusability by the wider community. Immediate data exchange is prioritized to facilitate interdependent tasks. Sensitive and restricted data (if any) will be generalized as needed and made publicly available following strict protocols. To ensure interoperability, BioEcoOcean will follow international data and metadata standards for oceanographic, biodiversity and geospatial data. Detailed information can be found in the BioEcoOcean's DMP (D1.1).

Message #3:

"By setting new standards for ocean research, we improve how we observe and report on marine environments."

BioEcoOcean strengthens standards and protocols for ocean observations, fostering improved modelling and

reporting. The project collaborates with OBPS and the global EOVS community to establish new best practices and standards where needed. Efforts also focus on increasing our capacity to assess and validate biological and ecosystem models, enhancing their reliability for regional and global biodiversity and climate assessments.

Message #4:

“Understanding and mitigating biodiversity loss is key to developing better policies and management strategies for ocean conservation.”

BioEcoOcean leverages observation networks to understand and mitigate biodiversity loss, informing adaptive management and policy decisions. Emerging tools and methods, such as camera networks, AI, eDNA, and high-resolution satellite imagery are used to increase the TRLs of BioEco EOVS and deepen our understanding of marine protection effectiveness and distribution ranges for such policy applications as MPAs. To comprehensively address drivers of biodiversity change, BioEcoOcean will look beyond environmental variables and explore socio-economic factors like fishing pressure and distance to market.

4.2.2 Communication tools

Logo and visual identity

The BioEcoOcean logo reflects the project's fundamental concept of cooperation and co-creation of the Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science. It symbolizes marine life, represented by seagrass and a dolphin, encircled by humans working together to protect the ocean. The logo consists of the project name with the signet being a part of the name, emphasising the project's main goals. The ocean colour palette distinctly conveys the project's focus.

The visual identity of BioEcoOcean is characterized by consistent graphical elements, including ocean floor images featuring vegetation or sea animals. These elements are utilized throughout all project communication activities to ensure easy recognition and distinctiveness.

Ready-to-use files (PowerPoint templates, social media templates) and branding are accessible to project partners on SharePoint. Detailed logo usage is described in the BioEcoOcean brand book (Annex 1)

Website

The BioEcoOcean project website was launched at the end of month 4 and serves as a focal point to ensure timely and efficient communication between project partners and target groups. The website will act as the central port of entry for the project and its outputs and will be seamlessly linked with social media such as Bluesky (this platform replaced X/Twitter in March 2025), LinkedIn, Facebook and YouTube and Spotify connecting with existing institutional social media accounts of the network partners.

The BioEcoOcean website, accessible from two domains: <https://www.bioecocean.eu> and <https://bioecocean.org/> serves as a crucial tool for disseminating and communicating key information about

the project. It offers an effective platform for project stakeholders and the public to gain a comprehensive understanding of the challenges addressed by the project and the solutions proposed. The website was developed as the first deliverable under Work Package 6 (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation) and was publicly launched on 31 May 2024.

The project website was designed to fulfil its main objectives which are to:

- ◆ Provide comprehensive information about the BioEcoOcean project, including its objectives, methodologies and expected impacts.
- ◆ Disseminate project results and outputs to stakeholders, including policy-makers, researchers, industry professionals and the general public.
- ◆ Facilitate communication and collaboration among project partners and stakeholders.
- ◆ Ensure transparency and accountability of project activities and progress.

Social media

In order to attract broader audiences' attention, engaging in communication on social media platforms is crucial. Thus, accounts on three platforms were launched: LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter), and Facebook. Each platform has its unique user base and content, which will influence our planned social media strategies based on the preferences of the targeted audience.

- ◆ LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/bioecoocean/>
- ◆ Bluesky <https://bsky.app/profile/bioecoocean.bsky.social>
- ◆ Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/61556248781551/>
- ◆ YouTube <https://www.youtube.com/@BioEcoOcean>
- ◆ Spotify <https://open.spotify.com/show/0DgCi1KMUJ4cz0lqwuQxz?si=5b6f141befa14a24>
- ◆ X <https://x.com/BioEcoOcean> (no longer used)

All partner institutions are encouraged to use their existing social media channels to tag the project in posts about project-related activities. Suggested content for social media communication can alternatively be sent to IO PAN for posting via the project social media channels. To provide better collaboration among WP6 partners the social media content calendar (Annex 2) for the project's social media platforms is used to plan the content in advance. Additionally, the daily communications planning is supported by Trello application used internally by the Communication Officers at IO PAN.

To facilitate an integrated social media campaign, we have compiled a list of BioEcoOcean partner accounts from targeted social media channels, as well as from other pertinent EU projects. In the coming weeks, the information will be supplemented with social media accounts of the target stakeholder groups (table 5).

Table 5: Inventory of social media accounts of project partners and selected other EU projects.

	Facebook	LinkedIn	X or/and Bluesky	YouTube
<i>Consortium members</i>				
Uppsala University (UU)	@ uppsalauniversitet	@ uppsala-university	@ uppsalauni	@ Uppsalauniversitet
The Technical University of Denmark (DTU)	@ dtudk	@ technical-university-of-denmark/	@ dtutweet	@ dtubroadcast
EuroGOOS	@ eurogoos	@ eurogoos	@ EuroGOOS	@ eurogoos
Universita di Pisa (UNIPi)	@ unipisaofficial	@ unipisa	@ Unipisa	@ VideoUNIPi
Centro Interdisciplinar De Investigacao Marinha E Ambiental (CIIMAR)	@ ciimar.up.pt	@ ciimar	@ CiimarUp	@ ciimarcomunicacao
Associação Para O Desenvolvimento Do Atlantic International Research Centre (Air Centre)	n/a	@ air-centre	@ AIRCentre_org	@ AIRCentre
Mercator Ocean International (MOI)	@ MercatorOcean	@ mercator-ocean	@ MercatorOcean	@ MERCATOROCEAN
Institute of Oceanology of Polish Academy of Sciences (IOPAN)	@ InstytutOceanologiiPAN	https://www.linkedin.com/company/iopan/	n/a	@ instituteofoceanologypan5519
United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO)	@ iocunesco	@ ioc-unesco	@ iocunesco	@ UNESCO
Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS)	@ GOOSocean	@ global-ocean-observing-system/	@ GOOSocean	@ goosocean
Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS)	n/a	@ ocean-biodiversity-information-system	@ OBISNetwork	@ oceanbiodiversityinformation6931
<i>Other EU Horizon Projects</i>				
ObsSea4Clim (Sister project)	n/a	@ obssea4clim	n/a	@ ObsSea4Clim

MARCO-BOLO	n/a	@marco-bolo/	@MARCOBOLO EU	n/a
OBAMA-NEXT	n/a	@obama-next-project-848927260	@ObamaNext	@obama-next
SEA-Quester	https://www.facebook.com/SeaQuesterEU	n/a	n/a	n/a
Ocean Citizen	@oceancitizen.eu	@oceancitizen	@oceancitizen eu	@oceancitizen eu
BLUE4ALL	n/a	@blue4all	@BLUE4ALLproject	n/a
BioGoeSea	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
Other Projects / Programmes / Networks				
GEO BON	https://www.facebook.com/BiodiversityObservationNetworkGEOBON	https://www.linkedin.com/company/geo-bon/	https://bsky.app/profile/geobon.org	http://www.youtube.com/@geobon1124
Marine Life 2030	n/a	https://www.linkedin.com/in/marine-life-b87a68226/	https://twitter.com/marinelifelife2030	http://www.youtube.com/@MarineLife2030
Phytodiverse	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD

We identified individual social media accounts of relevant stakeholder organizations to complete Table 6, as per stakeholder initial mapping just completed (MS6.1).

Table 6: Anticipated social media engagement with individual target audiences

Target audiences and primary social media					
	Facebook	LinkedIn	Bluesky	YouTube	Spotify
Academia		x	x		x
Public	x	x	x	x	x
Civil society	x	x	x	x	x
Policy makers		x	x		

We have several activities planned for 2024 on social media, examples can be seen in table 7.

Table 7: Social media planned activities for 2025/2026

Examples of near-term plans for BioEcoOcean social media campaigns	
Content	Date
Presentation and promotion of the focal living labs	Scheduled for 2025
Release of the the second promotional video	Scheduled for 2026
The next issue of the project newsletter	Ongoing
Presentation and promotion of EOV-focused research	Ongoing
BioEcoOcean ECOP series of posts on social media	Ongoing
Current news (posts or reposts) from the partners or other relevant projects	Ongoing
Advertising of the upcoming webinar series on BioEco EOVs	Ongoing
Next Episode of the Podcast Miniseries	Ongoing

Newsletter

We offer a possibility to subscribe to our newsletter through BioEcoOcean website. A quarterly newsletter is distributed to all registered users and stakeholders as well as the individual partner networks to share the progress of the work, upcoming events of the project and scientific and policy-related news. The newsletter subscription form is integrated with the website to encourage users to subscribe. The newsletter is distributed via email among subscribers and is accessible online on the website's dedicated page: <https://bioecocean.org/newsletter/>

Press Releases and other media outreach

IO PAN will liaise with any relevant press/media communication offices of the consortium partners to ensure that releases are coordinated, locally and internationally. Each consortium partner is responsible for alerting IO PAN to activities that can be promoted, and for providing the relevant content.

Each partner must also remember that, as stated in Art. 17 of the GA: "before engaging in a communication or dissemination activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform the granting authority."

Videos and podcasts

These widely targeted channels encourage dialogues between stakeholders, engage a range of audiences and communicate research developments more broadly in Europe and beyond. The BioEcoOcean will produce 4 videos and 3 podcasts during its lifetime. The first promotional video introducing the project was released after month 6 on YouTube: <https://youtu.be/dLUOTqS86b0?si=cZZKpOowrfFPutHK> and wo podcasts were released on Spotify: <https://open.spotify.com/show/ODgCi1KMUJ4cz0lqwuQxz?si=9d66b2456a884b1f>

Promotional materials

Printed promotional materials such as roll-ups, flyers, posters, postcards, banners and flags will be used at events (such as meetings, workshops, conferences and other public events) to increase the project's visibility. The communications team will provide partners with templates and ready-to-print files.

Digital promotional materials such as Word and PPT templates, social media visuals and post templates, banners and flyers, and ZOOM virtual background are accessible to project partners on SharePoint.

Webinars

A series of live-streamed webinars, hosted by “the Marine Biodiversity Networking Fridays” started in April 2025 with the Marine Biodiversity Networking Friday: Advancing ocean observations of marine life. It has been followed by the series on GOOS Biology and Ecosystems Essential Ocean Variables (BioEco EOVs).

All BioEcoOcean webinars are accessible from the project website: <https://bioecocean.org/webinars/>

Events

Conferences, workshops, stakeholder meetings, targeted briefings for policy makers. See more details and examples of planned events under Section 5.4.

4.2.3. EU visibility

According to Grant Agreement communication activities related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, and information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

5. Dissemination

In BioEcoOcean we are committed to maximizing the dissemination of project results by employing a variety of methods and activities, as briefly outlined below. BioEcoOcean is dedicated to disseminating its findings in accordance with the principles of open science, going beyond just open data. Successful dissemination hinges on timely and appropriate recognition of relevant stakeholder groups, and prioritizing their engagement, as

described in Section 3. Furthermore, WP6 will rely on knowledge of current and forthcoming processes at the science-policy interface, including cyclical scientific assessments and advice, anticipated policy changes, as obtained from WP1-5 and engaged stakeholders.

5.1 Open access publications in scientific journals

Publishing articles in peer-reviewed scientific journals is the primary method for disseminating BioEcoOcean's results to the academic community and beyond. Most of the articles will be generated by WP2-4, with the aim of achieving prolific output from each of the six living labs.

All articles will strictly adhere to the requirements for open-access publications. This means that project members need to do one of the following:

- ◆ Deposit their publication in a scientific repository to ensure open access.
- ◆ Publish their research in an open-access journal.

In both cases one, publications must also be deposited in a repository, even when publishing in an open access journal. It is important that authors [retain their article copyrights](#). While authors can choose to publish in open access or a subscription-based journals, project members should keep in mind that:

Only costs for Author Processing Charges in fully Open Access journals or platforms can be charged to the project.

Publishing costs are eligible for reimbursement only during the project's duration, provided that funds for open access publishing were allocated in the budget. Project partners should be cautious of journals which may misuse the Open Access model by charging high fees without providing adequate editorial services and peer review. BioEcoOcean project partners are also being encouraged to consider submitting research manuscripts and/or data articles using the free, open and transparent (open peer-review) research publishing model offered by Open Research Europe publication services. More details can be found at: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>.

Project partners are obliged to verify that the journal of their choice meets all the open access requirements, for example via the online Sherpa services (<https://beta.sherpa.ac.uk/>), or by checking with WP6. A comprehensive guide to adopting open science in publications can be found online at: <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-comply-with-horizon-europe-mandate-for-publications>

To facilitate adoption of open science principles in project publications (and other project outputs), we have set up a dedicated BioEcoOcean community on the open access repository Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/bioecoocean>) from where this information is being harvested automatically by the project website. In addition, news of publication will be shared internally via project SharePoint, and externally via project social media accounts, and authors' accounts where available. An application to join the

EU Open Research Repository Community is pending acceptance.

5.2 Open-access datasets, data synthesis and model products, model code

In BioEcoOcean, we have taken several steps to optimize means of disseminating observational data, data products and model results. The consortium is directed to the DMP to obtain specific guidance on how to ensure that the data and associated metadata are disseminated in a manner that makes them FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) and CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics) where relevant.

All model code will be shared freely and openly by depositing it on a public repository, such as GitHub. As in the case of data and scientific publications, EU funding must be acknowledged.

Each project member needs to contact WP6 upon the dataset or other product publication so that an adequate note appears on the project website and social media channels.

5.3 Project website, webinars and social media

All communication channels utilized in the project, particularly the website, social media platforms, and a series of project webinars, will be used as primary dissemination channels for every project output, with more coordinated and expanded campaigns planned in anticipation of KERs. Further details about the use of these communication channels can be found in Section 4.

5.4 Targeted online and face-to-face events

Face-to-face and online events with two-way interactions, such as workshops, webinars and briefings, are important dissemination tools for BioEcoOcean. To this end, we have planned to organize, or co-organize with partner organizations, dedicated events, often in conjunction with larger scientific or policy events that have the potential to gather selected project stakeholder groups and thus help relieve stakeholder fatigue.

A list of strategic dissemination events will be maintained as a living document on the project’s SharePoint for all partners to access and contribute to. These events will include those important for strategic dissemination of KERs according to overall project goals, and those important for outcomes of individual living labs. The type of events that BioEcoOcean will engage in is broad and depends on the target audiences.

Table 8 provides a snapshot of currently planned or already held dissemination events.

Table 8: List of completed (first 18 months) and planned key dissemination events. .

Event type	Name of event	Completed / planned
------------	---------------	---------------------

Scientific conferences and symposia	2024 Arctic Science Summit Week, February 2024 <i>Oral presentation at the Pan-Arctic Distributed Biological Observatories Community Meeting</i>	Completed
	2024 World Seagrass Conference, June 2024 <i>Oral presentations during scientific sessions</i> <i>Co-organization of the "Seagrass Futures" workshop</i>	Completed
	European Digital Ocean Forum, June 2024 <i>Participation in the panel: "The long-term vision for the European Digital Twin Ocean"</i>	Completed
	7 th International Marine Conservation Congress, October 2024 <i>Accepted oral presentations during scientific sessions</i>	Completed
	Baltic Sea Science Congress, May 2025	Completed
	2025 ESA Living Planet Symposium, June 2025	Completed
	XIII WIOMSA Symposium, September 2025	Planned
	2026 AGU Ocean Sciences Meeting, February 2026	Planned
	7 th World Conference on Marine Biodiversity, November 2026	Planned
Expert working group meetings and workshops	OBPS VIII Workshop, 15 October 2024 <i>Accepted co-organized session on Marine Life</i>	Completed
	GOOS BioEco Panel of Experts Meeting, <i>February 2025 Co-organized joint meeting</i>	Completed
	Joint meeting with the GOOS BioEco Panel of Experts, autumn 2026	Planned
Blueprint and other stakeholder workshops	The Status of Marine Biodiversity Monitoring in Europe, June 2024 <i>Participation</i>	Completed
	7 th International Marine Conservation Congress, October 2024 <i>Accepted organized Focus Group on "Organization of the Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science"</i>	Completed
	HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-8 Clustering Event, March 2025 <i>Co-organized joint meeting with the ObsSea4Clim project</i>	Completed
	2025 ICYMARE Conference, September 2025	Planned
	XIII WIOMSA Symposium, September 2025	Planned
Policy relevant events	15 th Annual Forum EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region, October 2024 <i>Registered to participate</i>	Completed
	UN Ocean Conference, June 2025 <i>TBD</i>	Completed

5.5 EU Commission tools

The EU Commission has made available a number of tools which BioEcoOcean plans to utilize to communicate, disseminate and foster exploitation of the key project results. We plan to:

- ◆ Boost the impact of project results through the Horizon Results Booster online services;
- ◆ Post articles and publications on CORDIS;
- ◆ Consider submitting news on any thought-provoking or innovation-driven outcomes to the Horizon Magazine;
- ◆ Share BioEcoOcean success stories through the Research and Innovation Success Stories;
- ◆ Use the Innovation Radar to strengthen connections with innovators and policymakers where relevant.

5.6 Nomination of experts to expert working groups

Apart from delivering new data products and research publications to inform the scientific assessment and advice processes, BioEcoOcean will identify possible opportunities for the nomination of BioEcoOcean scientists to participate in relevant regional and global expert working groups to share their expertise and newly acquired knowledge to address outstanding knowledge gaps and contribute to other relevant terms of reference of these groups.

5.7 Project clustering

Project clustering with sister projects from *HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-8*, and collaboration with other EU-funded projects, will be used to disseminate project results among those from the scientific community working on complementary research and applications. Specific means of using this approach are described in detail under Section 6. Table 9 provides a list of EU-funded projects with which BioEcoOcean has already established connections, or initiated joint activities, as well as those in planning.

Table 9: Areas of active and potential collaboration with other EU-funded projects for maximizing the project’s DEC potential

EU-funded projects	Areas of existing or potential collaboration	BioEcoOcean Living Lab
Active collaboration		
ObsSea4Clim	Blueprint development, EOVS Specification Sheets, EOVS-derived indicators, etc. <i>[representation at kick-off meetings; dedicated 1.5-day joint project meeting scheduled for March 2025]</i>	Blueprint Living Lab, others TBD
ECOTIP	Marine biodiversity and carbon cycling <i>[joint data product and Atlas planning]</i>	Marine Organic Carbon Atlas Living Lab
SEA-Quester	Marine biodiversity and carbon cycling	Marine Organic Carbon Atlas Living Lab

	<i>[joint data product and Atlas planning; data product development]</i>	
MARCO-BOLO	EOV (meta)data standards and protocols <i>[DMP developed in consultation]</i>	All Living Labs
OBAMA-Next	BioEco EOV data products, monitoring strategies	All Living Labs
NECCTON	BioEco EOV forecasting models	Pelagic Living Lab 1 & 2
Potential collaboration		
BioGeoSea	TBD	TBD
EDITOModellab	BioEco EOV forecasting models	Pelagic Living Lab 1 & 2
EDITO-Infra	BioEco EOV forecasting models	Pelagic Living Lab 1 & 2
DTO-BioFlow	Biodiversity data provision & management	All Focal Living Labs
BIOcean5D	Marine biodiversity mapping and modelling	All Focal Living Labs

6. Exploitation

6.1 Key Exploitable Results of BioEcoOcean

In BioEcoOcean, we have identified a number of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) which all together are expected to generate significant scientific, socio-economic and societal impacts. The project's exploitation strategy is therefore determined largely by these KERs listed below:

1. **Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science:** a novel interactive, question-based tool to support a holistic and integrated approach to ocean observations across its entire cycle from review and design to data collection and management, to application and policy.
2. **Advanced Biology and Ecosystems EOVS Specification Sheets:** a new, more fit-for-purpose, edition of a series of documents providing the Biological and Ecological (BioEco) observing communities with information on requirements and current status of building an integrated observing system, including data management and forecasting, for a given essential measurement.
3. **Strengthened forecasting tools for pelagic ecosystems and carbon fluxes** which enhance our capacity to model the key pelagic EOVS (plankton, sea turtles, fish) in epi- and mesopelagic zones to better understand the effect of functional diversity in energy flow and carbon fluxes under different environmental conditions.
4. **Spatial indicators for early-warning signals:** these will be explored based on emerging observing technologies and improved monitoring data, especially for coastal habitats.
5. **High-resolution satellite coastal data products for EOVS:** new remote-sensing products developed for seagrass and macroalgae EOVS.

6. **Pilot demonstration of a Marine Organic Carbon Atlas for the Arctic** which assembles available biological and biogeochemical data needed to better constrain our knowledge and capacity to model ocean carbon sequestration, with an initial focus on the Arctic Ocean.

BioEcoOcean will facilitate collaboration between multi-stakeholders (data providers, policy makers, academia and industry) leading to more efficient use of tools and data. Capacity building and networking activities will ensure the long-term use of BioEcoOcean KERs in the form of open access materials (publications, training events, social media) or training courses hosted on UNESCO's OTGA e-learning platform. See more details below.

6.2 Community of Practice Forum

BioEcoOcean will emphasize the importance of cross-domain integration and exploitation from month 1 to month 48. Central to this effort is the establishment and active engagement of a Community of Practice Forum (CoPF), co-led by the project, to synchronize efforts and coordinate the development of multi-disciplinary ocean observing. Such platforms offer a basis for transferring knowledge and innovation in the science-policy-practice system and for creating a framework for mutual exchange of the project results. The CoPF will also benefit from the wide network of contacts and collaborating entities and will align with "twin" projects funded under the same call and ongoing activities under the All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance, the UN Decade of Ocean Science, the GOOS BioEco panel, and MBON, as well as other relevant Horizon Europe-funded projects.

To ensure a broad and sustained impact, the CoPF will also extend invitations to additional networks and external partners, thereby fostering a collaborative environment that extends beyond the lifespan of the projects. The CoPF will serve as a platform for developing and disseminating recommendations for multi-disciplinary ocean observing and coordinated actions, such as observing plans and co-developed observing programs. These activities will contribute significantly to the implementation of the European Ocean Observing System Strategy 2023-2027.

Key activities include:

- ◆ **Clustering Events and Meetings:** Two major clustering events with the twin projects are scheduled (deliverables D6.3 and D6.4). Additionally, virtual meetings will be organized throughout the project to maintain continuous engagement and collaboration.
- ◆ **Policy Briefing:** The recommendations developed through the CoPF will be presented to policymakers at a dedicated policy briefing event (deliverable D6.7). This event will facilitate the translation of scientific and technical insights into actionable policy.
- ◆ **Workshops and Dialogues:** Holistic ocean observation and marine data integration will be promoted through cross-sector dialogues and workshops, including collaboration with relevant European Space Agency actions. These European events offer a vibrant platform for BioEcoOcean to connect with a broad and diverse community. Through active involvement in these gatherings, BioEcoOcean can foster

collaborations, share knowledge, effectively engage with a variety stakeholders, including policymakers, industry leaders, scientists and the general public.

The CoPF will promote a close interaction between members and foster the co-participation at events/activities/projects; develop recommendations for the multi-disciplinary ocean observing and coordinated actions contributing to the implementation of strategies from relevant actors of the marine biodiversity and coastal systems. As a result, the CoPF will become a collaborative space to share and create knowledge in the long-term.

By engaging a diverse range of stakeholders and maintaining a strong focus on cross-domain integration, BioEcoOcean will develop targeted strategies to enhance the coordination and effectiveness of ocean observing efforts. The focus will be on encouraging dialogues, engaging different sectors, creating opportunities to share knowledge, resources and perspectives across disciplinary boundaries. These stakeholders will include relevant EU projects and institutions, international organisations, policy and decision-makers, data providers and private sectors (Section 3).

7. Potential barriers to the outcomes and impacts achievement

Table 10 below identifies the risks and barriers that could potentially influence the uptake of BioEcoOcean results. In the project, we will assess and monitor these throughout, and update the table as needed.

According to the results of the Review of BioEcoOcean Critical Risks conducted in 2025, there are no major changes in risk assessment. The risk is still valid, and the current mitigation measures are effective.

Table 10: Risks and barriers to successful dissemination and exploitation of project results, along with proposed initial mitigation strategies.

Risks and barriers	Mitigation strategies
National, regional, and international policies and regulations may impact the implementation and scaling of the Blueprint, particularly in areas such as data sharing, privacy, and environmental protection.	The Blueprint will be co-created with relevant stakeholders across the lifetime of the project, including through scheduled dedicated workshop and consultation events. A stakeholder mapping and engagement strategy have been identified and will be reviewed as needed.
Lack of or low willingness of the various stakeholders to engage in the co-creation process and the availability of their time and resources	Effective communication means have been selected for the corresponding stakeholder groups initially mapped out for the project. Moreover, BioEcoOcean has already agreed to coordinate stakeholder engagement with the sister project ObsSea4Clim and plans to benefit from the connections established by other relevant projects (e.g. MARCO-BOLO).
Language barriers and differences in cultural norms could impact effective communication and collaboration.	We will utilize the value of the living labs with their broad geographical and thematic coverage, and a multi-national

	and multi-cultural project consortium, to proactively remove any language or cultural barriers to effective communication in local settings. Expertise in humanities and social sciences will be used to anticipate and proactively remove any potential issues (e.g. through careful survey design, workshop planning).
Obtaining adequate data from areas with limited human access (e.g. Marine Protected Areas, Military Zones)	In the project we will deploy field devices, such as cabled cameras, to obtain data from areas with limited human access.
Issues with adequate management of data	A comprehensive Data Management Plan (DMP) is put in place, with members of the OBIS Secretariat providing guidance and supervision over its implementation.

8. Monitoring and evaluation

Apart from a significant number of milestones and deliverables that will be closely monitored to ensure delivery of expected outcomes, BioEcoOcean has developed a number of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) which are listed in Table 11. All partners are expected to report on impact derived activities using the appropriate KPIs. To this end, WP6 has created an online “Impact Monitoring” form which is available on the project intranet (Figure 2). The form allows for collecting comprehensive information about a single dissemination activity, including the estimated target audience reached along with other project KPIs. The form will be improved by providing more pre-defined options and dropdown menus if needed, based on feedback from project partners.

Each partner is obliged to fill out the information on all dissemination activities in a timely manner, as soon as possible but at least every 18 months to contribute to the periodic assessment of project impact.

WP6, in consultation with the Steering Committee, will regularly review the KPIs and take measures as needed. Metrics will be tracked to allow adjustments in activities.

As far as the Blueprint development process is concerned, social scientists and socio-ecological systems analysts will also conduct research to analyze, assess, and evaluate the progress with the Blueprint. This approach creates a more holistic understanding of the Blueprint's impact and its potential to drive significant improvement in ocean observation and management.

Table 11: KPIs and a description of specific metrics for their tracking, with notes on partner roles and responsibilities in monitoring.

KPIs	Activity Type	Specific metrics	Initial Target	Updated Target at 18 months	Roles & responsibilities
KPI 1: Online Communications	Website	Number of active users	n/a	> 700	IOPAN
		Number of total views		> 10 000	
		Number of news articles published		> 50	
		<i>Tool: Google analytics</i>			
	Media coverage	Number of press articles, tv or radio new/interviews mentioning or featuring the project	n/a	10	IOPAN, with input from all partners
		Number of press releases		5	
		<i>Tool: impact tracking spreadsheet</i>			
	Social media engagement	Number of posts (all channels)	100 +	> 200	IOPAN
		Number of followers (all channels)	n/a	> 2 000	
		Number of views/impressions (all channels)	n/a	100k +	
		<i>Tool: analytics tools on social media platforms</i>			
	Webinar	Number of webinars produced/published	4	10	AIR Centre IOPAN
		Number of views (all webinars)	n/a	1 000	
		Number of registered attendees (all webinars)	n/a	1 000	
Number of countries from which the webinars were viewed		n/a	50		
<i>Tool: analytics tools provided by the webinar platform</i>					
Video	Number of videos produced and published	4	4	IOPAN	
	Number of views on YouTube (one video) <i>Tool: analytics tools provided by the video platform</i>	n/a	> 150		

	Podcast	<i>Number of podcasts released</i>	3	4	
		<i>Number of plays on Spotify</i> <i>Tool: analytics tools provided by the podcast platform</i>	n/a	> 100	
	Newsletter	Number of newsletters released;	8	4/year	IOPAN
		Number of subscribers	n/a	> 100	
KPI 2: Face-to-face meetings	Meetings	Number of face-to-face meetings (incl. Workshops) organized or co-organized;	4	10	All partners responsible for holding a given event
		Number of special sessions co-organised in international conferences	> 6	> 6	
		Number of meetings with GOOS BioEco Panel. <i>Tools: registration & attendance list</i>	2	2	
	Audience	<i>Number of stakeholder categories engaged</i>	n/a	12	
		<i>Number of early-career scientists engaged</i> <i>Tool: registration and attendance list</i>	n/a	TBD	
	Feedback	Number of feedback survey responses collected <i>Tool: event evaluation/feedback form</i>		50% of attendees	
KPI 3: Policy impact	Input to policy	Number of events organized at the science-policy interface	n/a	TBD	WP6 with input from partners and stakeholders
		Number of policy documents influenced by BioEcoOcean			
		Number of policy-makers engaged in project activities <i>Tools: impact tracking spreadsheet</i>			
KPI 4: Clustering and collaboration	Co-organization of initiatives	Number of partners (EU projects, other) engaged in co-organization of joint initiatives	n/a	TBD	EuroGOOS with input from all partners
		Number of CoPF participants	n/a	TBD	
		Number of EU projects engaged with directly	> 10	> 10	
		Number of clustering meetings organized.	2	2	

		<i>Tools: registration, attendance list & impact tracking spreadsheet</i>			
	Social Media Clustering	BioEcoOcean featured in other project social media, newsletters, or similar (e.g. number of posts from sister and other collaborating projects on BioEcoOcean's accounts) <i>Tool: Impact tracking spreadsheet</i>	n/a	> 10	IOPAN
KPI 5: Scientific output	Data collection and uptake	Number of datasets uploaded/published	> 15	> 15	UNESCO & IOPAN
		Number of views/downloads;	n/a	TBD	
		Number of new Level 4-6 data products <i>Tools: OBIS, Zenodo</i>	n/a	TBD	
	Publications	Number of open access peer-reviewed journal publications;	> 50	> 50	IOPAN
		Number of abstracts in conference proceedings			
Number of non-peer-reviewed publications <i>Tools: impact tracking spreadsheet, Zenodo</i>					
Conferences	Number of oral presentations; Number of poster presentations <i>Tools: Impact tracking spreadsheet, Zenodo</i>	> 50	> 50	IOPAN	
KPI 6: Co-design and co-creation	Survey engagement	Number of respondents to Blueprint surveys	n/a	>200	Collated by UU
	Workshop engagement	Number of workshop participants (online or in-person) actively contributing to the Blueprint development and/or testing	n/a	>100	Collated by UU
KPI 7: Training	Training courses	Number of Blueprint training courses and associated resources;	> 8	> 8	UNESCO
		Number of people trained <i>Tools: OTGA and other as needed</i>	> 100	> 100	
KPI 8: Best practices	Best practices	Number of new protocols and other best practice documents published (OBPS Repository)	1	TBD	All partners

Figure 2: Snapshot showing the online “Impact Monitoring” form which all project partners are asked to complete (accessible from SharePoint).

9. Conclusions

In conclusion, this Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan outlines a regularly update and comprehensive plan to ensure that the BioEcoOcean project’s research outcomes reach and benefit the target stakeholder groups collectively identified by the consortium, including scientists, policymakers, industry, and the public. Through targeted dissemination activities, we will share our findings and advancements in ocean science, focused on the research related to the BioEco EOVs but at the same time leading to better integration across all ocean science disciplines. Particular attention in the DEC Plan is given to the Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science, which relies on co-creation with relevant EU and global stakeholders throughout and beyond the project's duration. Exploitation strategies will focus on maximizing the practical application of our results, fostering innovation, and supporting policy development through close collaboration with other EU projects and international initiatives on the EU and global level. Our communication efforts will aim to engage and inform diverse audiences, enhancing the impact and visibility of our project. Together, these efforts will contribute to sustainable ocean management, biodiversity and climate resilience.

Annexes

Annex 1. BioEcoOcean brandbook

The BioEcoOcean brandbook has been developed by IOPAN in consultation with UU and other project partners. The full brandbook is accessible from the BioEcoOcean SharePoint platform. Below are images illustrating the type of information the brandbook contains.

2/ Colors of the sign

The colors of the sign are an important factor shaping the identity and perception of the brand. The colors of the sign and elements of the identification system should be as close as possible to the colors specified in CMYK, regardless of the reproduction technique. The parameters of the individual elements of the sign are presented below.

3/ Color version of the logo

It is recommended to use the color version of the logo in every possible application (printed materials and the internet). In special situations when it is not possible to use colors (e.g. in newspapers), a monochromatic or achromatic version can be used.

Color version

Monochromatic

Achromatic

4/ Logo protective box

The protective field of the logo was determined based on the width of the letters "Bio", which defines the space around the logo in which no graphic or text element can be placed. The exception is the graphic background on which the logo would be placed.

Minimum logo size

The minimum size of the logo has been designed so that the logo is legible not only on professional printouts but also on printouts from office printers. The total width of the logotype on the printout cannot be less than 40.0 mm (A). The exception are professional prints on offset machines, where a width of 30.0 mm is allowed (B).

5/ Permissible location variants

The page illustrates acceptable variants of the arrangement of logo elements.

6/ Applying a background

The page illustrates the basic color versions of uniform backgrounds, on which the mark may be used.

7/ Typography

The lettering is based on the following font:
- Montserrat

Montserrat Bold typeface
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuwxzyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNoprSTUwxyz
1234567890-=[\;':,-!/@#\$\$%^&*()_+{}:"'<>?

Lettering based on the example of the BioEcoOcean logo

8/ Font visualization

The key element is to maintain a uniform image on all presentation elements used by the company.

The following tips will help you properly use your company's image. The basic font used for official text documents is Montserrat, which is used in this book in various versions:

- 1) Document titles/headings
Montserrat Bold

In situations where it is necessary to use a universal font, e.g. the internet, e-mails, MS Office files or other correspondence files, then it is safest to use the Arial font. It is a sans-serif font, emphasizing modernity, and is included in every computer used today:

- 1) Document titles/headings
Arial Bold
- 2) The actual text
Arial Regular 13pt - to plain text

9/ Rollup visualization

Rollup size 85x200 cm

Annex 2. BioEcoOcean Social Media Content Calendar – Template

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	
1	Date	Day of the week	Topic	Content thread or category	Content format	Resources		Social Media Platform		
2								LinkedIn	Facebook	Twitter X
3										
4										
5	2024-03-02	Saturday								
6	2024-03-03	Sunday	World Wildlife Day	World Day	Repost					
7	2024-03-04	Monday		Partner News	Event					
8	2024-03-05	Tuesday	Research results	Other News	Post					
9	2024-03-06	Wednesday		Partner News	Repost					
10	2024-03-07	Thursday		Project News	Post					
11	2024-03-16	Saturday								
12	2024-03-17	Sunday								
13	2024-03-18	Monday		Project News	Repost					
14	2024-03-19	Tuesday	Workshop	Partner News	Event					
15	2024-03-20	Wednesday		Other News	Event					
16	2024-03-21	Thursday		Other News	Repost					
17	2024-03-22	Friday	World Water Day	World Day	Post					
18										
19										
20										
21										
22										
23										
24										
25										